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The Impact of Self-motivation on the Effective Job Performance of Staff: A Case Study of a Private Hospital in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

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Abstract

Like many other methodological motivations, the relationship between motivation and job satisfaction has been defined in many psychology studies. The model of impacts of rewards towards job satisfaction has been used by many organizations for their approach and reference. However, little research has been done to explore the impacts of self-motivation amongst staff at a private hospital in Kuala Lumpur towards their effective job performance. The paper is derived from factors that influence staff motivations and how these motivations can affect their job performance, using quantitative research data collection. The theory and results of the study are also briefly discussed. The Table of Reliability, Correlation and Regression analysis is presented in this thesis study for further reference. The results of this study suggest that the relationship between self-motivation and performance is a two-way relationship, where performance is also a key measure of a person's job satisfaction in his or her job. High job satisfaction, especially in the element of supervision, co-workers and the work itself can improve the emotions and behavior of employees in the workplace, as well as motivate employees to become more committed to attaining better performance.

Keywords: Self-Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Effective Job Performance

1. Introduction

Work is not only a source of income – it is more to the satisfaction of other needs such as the desire for competition, power, higher achievement as well as to determine the public opinion of their din. In this case, the individual will be happy, fun, and proud when their needs and satisfaction in the world of work have been met. On the other hand, negative feelings such as anger, resentment, boredom, and dissatisfaction will occur when their needs are not met; and this will have a big impact on the organization's progress. Work motivation is defined as the feeling or

emotional response of employees regarding aspects in a work situation; where employees who get encouragement and satisfaction in work will produce more quality and productive work (Kanfer et al., 2017). In other words, motivation is also defined as the essential factor for achieving one's goals (Azar & Sahar, 2021). It is contended that employees with extrinsic motivation require something in exchange for doing the duties assigned to them. Managers and coordinators must inspire them with awards to urge them to participate in the assigned responsibilities. It is essential in pushing and encouraging people to carry on with their daily activities. According to Andriani et al. (2018), work motivation refers to an employee's overall attitude towards his or her job. Moreover, according to Breugh et al. (2018), the study of work motivation is a description of attitude rather than behavior. However, both attitudes and behaviors have a cause and effect toward effective performance. Azar & Sahar (2021, p. 35) contend that employees that are intrinsically motivated frequently motivate themselves from inner side through internalised processes. This sort of individual is eager to learn and work independently to reach his or her goals. Employees that are self-motivated do not require other individuals or external motivators if they have their own inner drive. Azar & Sahar (2021) further add that the inner selves of self-motivated people are eager to achieve their objectives and fulfil their wishes. In the context of self-motivation, newly employed individuals will accept whatever form of work is offered; however, when they have been working for a long time, the view on employment becomes broader and more meaningful (Çetin & Aşkun, 2018). Based on the above issues, this study intends to explore impacts of self-motivation amongst the employees at a private hospital in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia on the effective job performance.

1.1 Self-Motivation on the Effective Job Performance

Past studies have shown that with the existence of work motivation and high commitment to the organization, an individual can exhibit behavior known as pro-social citizenship, which involves the attitude of liking and helping colleagues, helping and prioritizing customer interests as well as being willing to cooperate with each other (Olafsen et al., 2018). This includes assisting hospital patients in carrying out tasks, striving and having awareness to protect healthcare departmental interests and symptoms such as fire, theft, and damage by irresponsible people. Another organizational researcher, Demirhan et al. (2020) conducted a study on the hospital nurse and categorized three main factors that can influence job motivation. These were job characteristics (rewards, promotion opportunities, clear responsibilities, and opportunities for the use of skills), organizational characteristics (commitment to the hospital organization, good relationships with supervisors and doctors), and individual characteristics (age, race and gender). The researcher also found that improvements in all factors related to job characteristics and organizational characteristics have a positive effect in further increasing work motivation among hospital nurses.

For individual characteristics, the positive effect is only shown with age increase, while the influence of gender does not play an important role in determining such satisfaction. This is also in line with the recommendations of Ahlstedt et al. (2019) who have recommended several ways to increase work motivation amongst hospital staff such as the clarification of responsibilities and areas of responsibility, reducing control over employees, providing opportunities to plan and perform their own tasks, and giving authority and creativity to employees in carrying out their duties. In terms of personal factors that can affect job satisfaction, Abidin (2020) has categorized these personal factors of affecting job satisfaction into five main categories namely age, gender, race, personality, and cognitive abilities. Job motivation among hospital staff usually increases with increased employee age as displayed by a "U" shaped distribution. As for gender characteristics, male employees generally show a higher level of work motivation compared to women, while minority segments in an organization often have low work motivation. As for the personality aspect, a high locus of internal control and self-concept often shows a high degree of work motivation; however, it was also found that individuals who are fit and have cognitive abilities tend to find routine tasks boring and this lowers their level of motivation to work. According to Purwanti et al. (2020), the differences between male and female workers also depend on job factors (autonomy, use of skills, career development opportunities, status and salary), family factors (responsibility for family burdens) and social factors (education, age, religion and degree) can also influence work motivation differences between gender. In addition, Gunawan et al. (2019) stated that female workers will be more motivated to work than men if the aforementioned factors were evenly distributed among them.

A study by Breed et al. (2020) for nine countries in Europe found differences in the level of work motivation amongst hospital staff for these countries. In most of the countries surveyed, researchers found that more than 10% of employees said they did not get satisfaction or motivation from work. On the other hand, for countries categorized as industrial countries, only 3% of workers have high career motivation. Workers in the Republic of Ireland have the highest level of motivation and job satisfaction compared to other European countries. This situation exists as a result of the work culture and work patterns in Ireland which are less stressful and prioritize strong social relations. This finding is also supported by Djukic et al. (2020) where he found work stress that determines the level of motivation and satisfaction, as well as factors of economic and social conditions of a country. Organizational practices related to autonomy play an important role in determining work motivation among hospital staff (Phinari & Bernarto, 2020). The results of the study have proven that there are no differences in the level of work motivation between genders in organizations that give autonomy to female employees. Female employees at the management level are given more responsibilities. In addition, work motivation is also found to depend on one's age and duration of work. Manning (2016) found that age gives a "U" shaped distribution in determining work motivation. According to him, the level of work motivation amongst hospital staff at the beginning level is high, before decreasing and then increasing again as age increases until the end of the period of service.

Similarly, Ardita et al. (2019) found that only 5% of hospital staff aged 35 years and above do not have work motivation when compared with young hospital staff who mostly show a low level of work motivation. This opinion is supported by Hidayah and Fadila (2019) that staff of local with higher education positions prioritize a love for work as very important in determining their motivation and satisfaction. Recognition from employers and peers as well as academic freedom occupy the next place on the list of interests. Thus, it is important to explore what the impact of self-motivation is on the effective job performance amongst staff of private hospitals in Kuala Lumpur. Organizational behaviour researchers – Doloh et al. (2018) also formulated a similar matter where according to the authors, the importance of work motivation should be prioritized since the absence of motivation will cause behaviors such as skipping and changing work. For the employees themselves, low motivation will tend to exhibit physical and mental health disorders. Therefore, employees who have a high level of work motivation are more to be profitable and an important asset to the organization. According to Pundati et al. (2018), there is a positive relationship between work motivation and an individual's excellence, physical and mental health, and life satisfaction. They added that dissatisfaction in work can evoke various feelings such as frustration, truancy, job changes, mental and physical health disorders as well as internal conflicts within the organization. Therefore, it is very important to ensure that staff motivation is consistently maintained to avoid frustration, burn out, and a lack of interest towards their job which causes them to eventually leave the organization.

Besides, Sutarto et al. (2017) recommend every organization should always strive to improve its excellence in all aspects, especially in developing and enhancing knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values amongst all levels of its members. With this, the organization can increase the expectations of staff and organizations to achieve organizational excellence. The systematic control and management of human resource departments are also important in increasing employees' motivation, organizational productivity, and further achieving national vision. In this regard, management needs to foster good relations amongst employees, create a harmonious organizational climate and ensure that employees have high loyalty to their workplace organization. Therefore, based on the above research, this study seeks to explore the factors that influence staff motivation. The issue of maintaining staff loyalty to their organization is very challenging. However, from the various research studies available, the potential of retaining staff in an organization by ensuring staff motivation and job satisfaction is crucial because it will influence the staff to work more effectively and passionately, as well as clearly understanding the organization mission and becoming an important asset to the organization. In addition, from the study, the organization can help identify factors that influence staff motivation and what the organization can provide to ensure staff remain motivated throughout their career and achieve job satisfaction.

1.2 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is the feeling experienced by an employee towards the work he or she does. This feeling of satisfaction will cause a person to always want to work with a full sense of responsibility (Ghazali & Turiman,

1995). Several studies have shown that employees who have a high level of job satisfaction will be more productive, as well as produce quality and good work (McNeese-Smith, 1996; Mullins, 1989; Nash, 1985; Schultz, 1982). While employees who are at a low level of job satisfaction tend to cause various problems to the organization such as truancy, lateness, and disciplinary problems (Lussier, 1990). Employee job satisfaction is very important for an organization because employees with job satisfaction tend to carry out their work sincerely and not complain about the work and instructions given. Even if the staff are not satisfied with the work that they do, they still complete their work even if they are not diligent (French & Seward, 1983; Locke, 1988). Katzell (1975) associated job satisfaction with feelings, the extent to which an employee likes or dislikes his or her work. According to him, employees are satisfied when they have a positive attitude towards work and job prospects, as well as being able to animate their work in accordance with their lives. Apart from that, according to Wan Ahmad (2000), job satisfaction is considered as a feeling of fun or positive emotions resulting from the evaluation of positions held in the work environment.

1.3 Relationship Between Employees Motivation and Job Satisfaction

The relationship between employee motivation and job satisfaction is also currently being studied and some researchers (Heneman et al., 1988; Igalens & Roussel, 1999; Pool, 1997) have concluded that job motivation and job satisfaction should be investigated separately, so that the factors influencing the results of the study are easier to identify and better understand. Herzberg (2003) Two-Factor Theory identifies intrinsic factors and hygiene factors that tend to be extrinsic factors. Herzberg argues that these factors lead to job satisfaction because they meet individual needs to realize themselves (Maslow, 1954; Tietjen & Myers, 1998). In contrast, the Theory of Expectations as developed by Porter and Lawler (1968), argues that pay-for-performance systems can influence job satisfaction (Ferris, 1977; Igalens & Roussel, 1999). Supporting this view, Pool (1997) studied the relationship between job motivation and job satisfaction and found a significant positive relationship between them; where as work motivation increases, job satisfaction also increases. Although the argument that the positive relationship between extrinsic factors and job satisfaction is more dominant, Frey (1997) gives an opposing opinion. Frey argues that intrinsic factors can increase because of work improvement programs that contribute to work ethic improvement (Frey, 1997).

When the pleasure of an employee advances their work, the instinctive factor can affect the extrinsic factor (Frey, 1997). However, researchers who support the theory of self-determination argue that the pay-for-performance system can have a positive effect on intrinsic factors by supporting and promoting employee autonomy and self-esteem (Deci & Ryan, 2008; Gagné & Deci, 2005). However, this theory does not state whether extrinsic motivation will decrease, or if intrinsic factors increase. Job satisfaction is also associated with performance (Halkos & Bousinakis, 2010), quality (Wood et al., 2012), and performance efforts (Apostle et al., 1985; Muse & Stamper, 2007; Pettijohn et al., 2008). Leach (1998) conducted a study on job satisfaction and performance among salespeople.

Studies have shown that motivational control and emotional control affect sales performance. As performance improves, job satisfaction also increases. Job satisfaction is also associated with motivation (Egan et al., 2004). From research on hospital department employees in large companies, studies show that job satisfaction positively influences motivation for learning transfer (Egan et al., 2004). In addition, this study also concludes that job satisfaction is related to motivation to share knowledge. According to Gholizade et al. (2014), in their study of 250 employees in the field of healthcare and public hospitals in the Boyerahmad Kohkiluyeh in Iran found that job satisfaction can be a major factor influencing work motivation and commitment to the study.

1.4 Relationship between Factors Influencing Self-Motivation and Effective Job Performance Among Employees

There are various factors that influence the effective job performance of employees. With the increase in employees' self-motivation, job performance is expected to become more effective. Firstly, a good working environment influences self-motivation and results in effective job performance (Ghaffari, Shah, Burgoyne, Nazri & Salleh, 2017). Working environment can be defined as the place employees work which affects their self-motivation and job performance (Ghaffari et al., 2017). This is key so that employees not only increase their

motivation to do more but also become more involved in their work, contributing to the growth of their respective organizations (Ghaffari et al., 2017). The result of all this will be absolute satisfaction for employees, increasing productivity of work, and increased organization benefits (Ghaffari et al., 2017).

The second factor influencing self-motivation and effective job performance is appreciation given by employer to the employees (Geiger, 2022). Appreciation can be defined as employers showing gratitude or the way the management of an organization thanks their employees (Geiger, 2022). Every employee who works in an organization must like when the work they do is appreciated by the employer or other colleagues (Geiger, 2022). Employers should always give praise for achievements by employees (Geiger, 2022). Employees who received appreciation at least once a year showed an improvement in terms of job performance compared to those who did not receive any direct appreciation from the organization since appreciation boosts self-motivation (Geiger, 2022).

The third factor is growth opportunities as gaining self-motivation and effective job performance (Faisal & Al-Rasheed, 2021). The potential for employees to be promoted or gain skill training and development can be summed up as a growth opportunity (Faisal & Al-Rasheed, 2021). The ability to evolve in an organization can increase employee self-motivation to be loyal and dedicated to work (Faisal & Al-Rasheed, 2021). One of the most crucial factors in fostering employee engagement is growth (Faisal & Al-Rasheed, 2021). If employees had more opportunity to grow, they will push their self-motivation to become better employees and show positive job performance (Faisal & Al-Rasheed, 2021).

1.5 Relationship between Impacts of Self-Motivation and Effective Job Performance Among Employees

Self-motivation of employees impacts job performance. Firstly, self-motivation enhances productivity of effective job performance (Mikhailova, 2021). In general, work productivity is measuring quality and quantity in certain units to achieve results and effective job performance (Mikhailova, 2021). Thus, productivity is related to inputs and outputs (Mikhailova, 2021). Elements included in work productivity and effectiveness which are related to maximum job performance by gaining self-motivation (Mikhailova, 2021). Second, self-motivation leads the focus of staff to a direction which the result is to accomplish effective job performance (Mikhailova, 2021). When employees are self-motivated to accomplish the job given, good focus and planning are needed for which job to be accomplished first (Mikhailova, 2021). Employees can prioritize their job list depending on deadline (Mikhailova, 2021).

Even for employees who have had difficulties and challenges during the job, self-motivation and a positive attitude helps employees maintain their focus on the vision and objectives until they achieve effective job performance (Geiger, 2022). Thirdly, self-motivation will ensure that employees achieve personal job growth in effective job performance. Self-motivation in personal job growth in terms of knowledge and skill is important for employees achieving effective job performance (Geiger, 2022). Hence, self-motivation can drive personal growth in terms of job promotion since it enhances job performance (Geiger, 2022).

Employees need to realise that self-motivation helps them a lot with effective job performance and gives positive impact to their personal job growth (Geiger, 2022).

1.6 Research Questions

1. What are the factors that influence self-motivation towards effective job performance of staff at a private hospital in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia?
2. What is the impact of self-motivation on the staff's effective job performance at a private hospital in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia?

1.7 Limitation of Study

The limitation of this study is that only one issue was examined – staff motivation at a private hospital in Kuala Lumpur. Thus, it is advisable to explore further in future regarding the challenges faced by organizations in terms

of retaining jobs or increasing staff wages. This study also focuses on collecting data using a questionnaire only in Kuala Lumpur.

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

Quantitative research is used for this research design where a questionnaire survey was used to collect data from respondents to achieve the research goal.

2.2 Sampling Procedure

The population study for this research was typically considered from one private hospital in Kuala Lumpur and its total was 985 staff of the hospital. The questionnaire was distributed to the managers, executive staff, assistant managers, senior managers, and finally head of departments through the WhatsApp and Telegram links. Those staff who were available and free at their office time at the hospital were only able to respond the researchers' questionnaire (100 respondents), which is the sample size of this project. The convenience sampling method was selected for this study.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

The data analysis result of this study where the researcher will show the outcome of the SPSS analysis for readers to digest. SPSS offers a program that assists researchers with complex data analysis needs and is used widely by health researchers.

Figure 1: Gender Status

Based on Figure 1, the summary of gender status can be found where the majority of respondents were female with a total of 88 participants and only 12 male participants.

Figure 2: Age Status

Based on Figure 2, the summary of age status shows that the majority of respondents were 21 years and above (59 respondents), followed by 20-year-old participants (26 respondents), and finally 18-year-old participants (15 respondents) who represented the minority.

Figure 3: Race Status

Based on Figure 3, the summary of race status showed that many respondents were Malay with a total of 74 respondents, followed by a total of 18 Chinese respondents, and only 8 Indian participants.

Figure 4: Job Position Status

Based on Figure 4, the summary of job position found that many of the respondents were managers (27 respondents), followed by executive staff (20 respondents), assistant managers (14 respondents), senior managers (16 respondents), and finally head of departments (9 respondents).

Figure 5. Marital Status

Based on Figure 5, the summary of marital status found that the majority of respondents were married with a total of 72 respondents, followed by respondents who were single with a total of 17 respondents, and other status' consisted of only 11 respondents.

Figure 6: Number of Children Status

Based on Figure 6, the summary of number of children found that the majority of the respondents (26 respondents) have one child, 21 respondents have 2 to 3 children, 17 respondents have 4 children, and only 15 respondents stated that they do not have children.

Figure 7: Education Qualification Status

Based on Figure 7, the summary of education qualifications found that many respondents with diploma certificates totaled 62 respondents, degree holders made up a total of 22 respondents, 14 respondents hold a master’s degree, and finally only 2 respondents hold a doctorate.

Figure 8: Monthly Income Status

Based on Figure 8, the summary of income per month found that the majority of respondents earn RM2,000 to RM2,999 (37 respondents), followed by an income of RM3,000 to RM3,999 (25 respondents), an income of RM4,000 to RM4,999 (9 respondents), and finally only 4 respondents shared that they earn RM5,000 above.

Figure 9: Monthly Income Status

Based on Figure 9, the summary of organizational tenure status found that the majority of respondents had a 5-to-9-year tenure with the organization (46 respondents), followed by 29 respondents with more than 10 years at the organization, and only 25 respondents with less than 4 years at the organization.

Figure 10: Positional Tenure Status

Based on Figure 10, the summary of positional tenure found that the majority of respondents stated that they have between 5 to 9 years at their respective positions (58 respondents), followed by another 22 respondents holding their job positions for more than 10 years, and only 20 respondents with less than 4 years tenure.

Table 1: Summary of Factors that Influence Self-Motivation

Variables	SD	D	PA	A	SA
I am happy with my benefit plans from the organization.	0	0	2	28	70
My organization cares about employee's welfare.	0	0	2	28	70
I feel energetic at my job.	0	0	10	25	65
I feel energetic to going work daily.	0	0	3	30	67
I am enthusiastic about my job.	0	0	2	25	73
My job inspires me.	0	0	0	20	80
I am proud of the work I do.	0	0	0	17	83
I feel happy when I work with intensity onmy job.	0	0	2	28	70
My work gives me a feeling of personal accomplishment.	0	0	0	11	89
I will most probably stay in this job in the foreseeable future.	0	0	3	13	84
I am motivated to contribute more for my organization.	0	0	2	25	73

Note SD = Strongly Disagree D = Disagree PA = Partly Agree A = Agree SA = Strongly Agree

Based on Table 1, the summary of factors that influence self-motivation found that most respondents strongly agreed with “My work gives me a feeling of personal accomplishment” with 89 respondents. “I am happy with my benefit plans from the organization”, “My organization cares about employee welfare”, and “I feel happy when I work with intensity on my job” represented 70 respondents who strongly agreed. “I feel energetic at my job” represented 65 respondents, “I feel energetic going to work daily” represented 67 respondents, “My job inspires me” represented 80 respondents, all of whom strongly agreed. “I am enthusiastic about my job” and “I am motivated to contribute more for my organization” were strongly agreed by 73 respondents. “I am proud of the work I do” represented by 83 respondents and “I will most probably stay in this job in the foreseeable future” represented by 84 respondents who strongly agreed with these statements.

Table 2: Summary Impacts of Self-Motivation

Variables	SD	D	PA	A	SA
I feel satisfied with my good job performance.	0	0	0	10	90
I feel that self-motivation will lead to effective performance of my present job.	0	0	0	20	80
My job makes me feel like a valued member of this organization.	0	0	2	28	70
My job is meaningful and make me feel to perform better.	0	0	3	13	84
I am happy because the organization has given me the opportunity for career advancement.	0	0	2	25	73

Note SD = Strongly Disagree D = Disagree PA = Partly Agree A = Agree SA = Strongly Agree

Based on Table 2, the summary impacts of motivation found that most respondents strongly agreed with “I feel satisfied with my good job performance” with 90 respondents. “I feel that self-motivation will lead to effective performance of my present job” represented 80 respondents, “My job makes me feel like a valued member of this organization” represented 70 respondents, “My job is meaningful and makes me want to perform better” represented 84 respondents, and “I am happy because the organization has given me the opportunity for career advancement” represented 73 respondents, all of whom strongly agreed.

Table 3: Summary Effective Job Performance of Private Hospital Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia Staff

Variables	SD	D	PA	A	SA
My supervisors praise me and give me recognition when I perform my job well.	0	0	5	30	65
My supervisors take appropriate action to solve problems in a timely manner.	0	0	15	65	72
My supervisors provide the support I need to succeed.	0	0	2	28	70
My pay is appropriate for the role I have in this organization, compared to similar roles at other organizations.	0	0	20	20	60
I am reasonably paid for the extra contribution I make to the organization.	0	0	20	20	60

Note SD = Strongly Disagree D = Disagree PA = Partly Agree A = Agree SA = Strongly Agree

Based on Table 3, the summary of effective job performance of staff at a private hospital in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia found that most respondents strongly agreed with “My supervisors take appropriate action to solve problems in a timely manner” with 72 respondents. “My supervisors praise me and give me recognition when I perform my job well” represented 65 respondents, and “My supervisors provide the support I need to succeed” represented 70 respondents, all of whom strongly agreed. Moreover, “My pay is appropriate for the role I have in this organization, compared to similar roles at other organizations” and “I am reasonably paid for the extra contribution I make to the organization” represented 60 respondents, all whom strongly agreed.

Table 4: Summary of Reliability Analysis

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Factors that influence self-motivation	0.86
Impacts of self-motivation	0.83
Effective job performance of private hospital Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia	0.84

Table 4 presents three variables that had been proposed in the questionnaire and a significant level of Cronbach's Alpha that is greater than 0.80 is observed. Thus, it can be assumed that all items can be moved to the next level since it was recommended and applicable for this study.

Table 5: Summary of Correlation Analysis

Correlations

	Factors Influencing Self-Motivation	Effective Performance of Private Hospital Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia	Job of Hospital Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
Effective Job Performance of Private Hospital Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia	Pearson Correlation .519**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed) <.001		
	N 100	100	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

A Pearson correlation coefficient is determined to examine the relationship between the factors influencing self-motivation (IV1) and impacts of self-motivation (IV2) towards effective job performance at a private hospital in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia (DV). Table 4.15 shows that there is moderate and positive significant correlation between factors influencing self-motivation (IV1) and effective job performance of private hospital Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia (DV) ($r = .519$, $p < .01$). There is moderate and positive significant correlation between impacts of self-motivation (IV2) and effective job performance at a private hospital in Kuala Lumpur.

Table 6: Summary of Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.789 ^a	.623	.615	0.307

a. Predictors: (Constant), Factors Influence Self-Motivation, Impacts Self-Motivation

Table 7: Summary of ANOVA

ANOVA					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	31.93	2	7.982	84.54	0.00 ^b
Residual	19.36	97	0.094		
Total	51.29	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Effective_Job Performance

b. b. Predictors: (Constant), Factors_Influence_Self-Motivation, Impacts_Self-Motivation

Table 8: Summary of Coefficients

Coefficients						
Model	Sum of Squares	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	Constant	0.61	0.301		4.48	0.000
	Factors_Influence_Self-Motivation	0.38	0.067	0.40	5.73	0.000
	Impacts_Self-Motivation	0.23	0.07	0.23	3.23	0.001

a. Dependent Variable: Effective Job Performance

A multiple linear regression was implemented to examine whether factors influence self-motivation (IV1) and impacts of self-motivation (IV2) significantly describe effective job performance of private hospital Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia (DV). Based on Table 6, the outcome of the multiple regression analysis indicated that the model explicated 61.5% of the variance. Based on Table 7, the model significantly described effective job performance of private hospital Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia (DV), $F(2, 97) = 84.54$, $p < .01$. Based on Table 8, the standardized coefficient beta, factors influence self-motivation (IV1) ($B = 0.40$, $p < .01$) significantly described the highest variance in effective job performance at a private hospital in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia (DV) compared to impacts of self-motivation (IV2) ($B = 0.23$, $p < .01$). Hence, factors that influence self-motivation is the most independent variable (IV) related to effective job performance at the private hospital (DV).

The findings of this study show that the percentage of staff with high work motivation in the selected private hospital is high. Although there are differences depending on job position level, as an effort to further enhance the existing motivation, both agencies involved need to focus more on matters related to opportunities for staff Puteri Hospital regarding their future progress, prioritizing the use of staff-owned skills as well as providing more space to set goals at work. This matter is important because the findings of the study show that most healthcare departments lack motivation in job performance.

In this regard, to complete the job for their future progress, Odukah (2016) suggested greater exposure to training, courses and seminars, information on adequate assignments, and responsibility in making decisions related to work. This phenomenon in the agency may be related to the view of Lambrou et al. (2010) which is based on the belief that the behaviour of employees is difficult to change, and hence certain organizations do not provide courses and training for employees as an important factor towards employee development for future progress. According to the researcher Lambrou et al. (2010), many studies conducted in the Malaysia have succeeded in proving that employees are given adequate training and exposure to the task-related matter, being able to further enhance their own progress and development. Pardoe et al. (2018) has stated that to overcome this problem, employers should also be aware that the task of completing job for the sake of their future progress is not the responsibility of the employee but rather the duty of the employer. This is because hospital employees who are well-versed in their knowledge and experience in matters related to work will bring benefits to the organization itself.

This needs to be realized and implemented by employers continuously throughout the career period of employees to deal with changes in the organization, especially changes involving technological and communication skills works particular (Chigozie et al., 2018). The importance of this is in line with the findings by Machara and Jain (2016) where they found that the opportunity to use skills to be one of the main determinants in influencing individual work motivation. To realize this, the work system needs to be made adaptable and timely, especially for tasks that are too simple or repetitive work (routine) as it can cause the employee to become complacent. The staff in this study need to be given more complex and challenging tasks to hone their skills in problem solving, decision making, and job creativity.

It is also proven that employees with low work motivation have a high tendency to look for other jobs. In this case, the employers for both agencies need to take specific steps to overcome this since large expenses are required especially when appointing and retraining new employees (Panait & Panait, 2018). There is separation in the working group which may pose a major problem if it involves significant assignments (Cătălina, 2018). It also tends to be detrimental to the organization if these employees are the "star performers" in the agency (Chromjakova, 2016). Every organization must strive to retain existing employees and action needs to be taken to create loyalty among them. This includes improving the work climate as a reward system and fair recognition, assignment of clear duties and responsibilities, fostering a harmonious relationship between management and staff, and the more serious application of departmental identities.

In comparison, relatively low job motivation among the staff in this study at state agencies may be related to its closed service management system. Agencies that have closed service management are usually lagging slightly behind in terms of change and innovation due to the lack of exposure to change. In this regard, individuals at the top management level need to be exposed to many courses, seminars and training, especially at the national level to further expand their knowledge towards the formation of effective leadership and management patterns. Francis-Coad et al. (2019) conducted a longitudinal study to compare the changes that exist in the organizational climate and work motivation based on the reforms that have been implemented in line with the changing global environment. The findings of this study are important as a benchmark in guiding the management of the organization involved to lead towards the achievement of the vision and mission of the organization. This is necessary because the study that has been carried out has proven that improvement efforts in the climate of the organization can change the position of work motivation to a higher level.

4. Conclusion

Hospital staff are the most important assets in an organization whose role is to determine the direction and goals of the organization to be implemented and achieved (Reyazi & Aghaei, 2019). When new hospital staff joins an organization, the individual automatically agrees to be loyal and contribute their effort, skill, and knowledge to achieve the organization's goals (Reyazi & Aghaei, 2019). Therefore, private hospital staff need to fully commit to the organization, and further increase their productivity through responsibility (Reyazi & Aghaei, 2019).

Self-motivation will create a positive, productive, and innovative organizational climate (Reyazi & Aghaei, 2019). Through self-motivation of hospital staff, more action is encouraged, and the employee's thinking is stimulated to believe that he/ she has the potential and ability to continue contributing to the progress and success of the private hospital (Reyazi & Aghaei, 2019). The self-motivation of staff is essentially a form of recognition to the quality of work shown by the staff because quality employees are the main asset of an organization (Reyazi & Aghaei, 2019). The quality of the work includes how it is carried out and whether the output successfully meets the required expectations (Reyazi & Aghaei, 2019).

Trustworthy and responsible staff at a private hospital will increase effective job performance, while aspirations will be achieved if there are reforms in thoughts and actions that benefit the country (Siew, Chitpakdee & Chontawan, 2020). As well as encouraging innovation, this study endeavors to improve effective job performance amongst the staff at a private hospital by ensuring it is at the top of the Malaysian government's agenda amid an era of rapid change and disruptive technology (Siew et al., 2020). This study is a contribution for Malaysia in its journey of becoming a developed country, depending on the ability to increase the productivity level of employees (Siew et al., 2020). Therefore, having quality hospital staff at all levels in every department can enhance effective job performance because quality employees are a translation to the success of the organization, producing first-class human resources that in turn become valuable assets for organizational excellence in the long-term (Siew et al., 2020).

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